

JOURNAL OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGY

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#348 SUMMARY

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SUBMISSION

Authors	Andrej Poleev
Title	Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.
Original file	348-1072-1-SM.DOC 2019-09-03
Supp. files	None ADD A SUPPLEMENTARY FILE
Submitter	Andrej Poleev
Date submitted	September 3, 2019 - 07:56 AM
Section	ARTICLES
Editor	None assigned
Author comments	Dear editor,

I write to inform you and the whole scientific community about my decision to liquidate the company and charity IPA LBG registered in England and Wales under registered numbers 3496765 and 1071752 respectively, to terminate its activity and the activity of its constituent organisations due to reasons explained in my book „Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis“ and in consequence of the symptomatic appearance of the psychopathological condition related to Ganser syndrome by which the members of IPA LBG are obviously affected. At the same time, in order to fulfill the will of Sigmund Freud I announce the reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.

Secondly, I confiscate all assets and property owned by IPA LBG and its constituent organisations for the purpose of said reestablishment.

Thirdly, I prohibit the usage of terms „psychoanalysis“, „psychoanalyst“ and „psychoanalytic“ and their equivalents in other languages by members of the IPA LBG, its constituent organisations, other companies, organizations and associations or by any person in relation to the professional designation.

Fourthly, to be qualified to perform psychoanalysis and to be designated as psychoanalyst, candidates should be examined by at least one supervisor and member of the reestablished International Psychoanalytical Association, and should demonstrate proficient knowledge of psychoanalysis and ability to perform it without any guidance. Every successful proof of ability will be registered,

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poleev

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AUTHOR

Submissions

[Active \(1\)](#)

[Archive \(0\)](#)

[New Submission](#)

INFORMATION

[For Readers](#)

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FONT SIZE

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published and legally attested in order to guarantee the quality standard and individual accountability.

Dr. Andrej Poleev

Reference.

A. Poleev. Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis. Print edition 2019.
<http://enzymes.at/download/ppe.pdf>

STATUS

Status	Awaiting assignment
Initiated	2019-09-03
Last modified	2019-09-03

SUBMISSION METADATA

[Click to Print This Page](#)

[EDIT METADATA](#)

AUTHORS

Name	Andrej Poleev	Affiliation	—

Corresponding author

TITLE AND ABSTRACT

Title	Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.
Abstract	Due to reasons explained in my book „Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis“ and in consequence of the symptomatic appearance of the psychopathological condition related to Ganser syndrome by which the members of IPA LBG are obviously affected, I announce the reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.

ISSN: 2499-6904

Final Decision for Manuscript "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association."
Nov 5 2019

Valentina Barberi <journal@jpsychopathol.it>

To: Andrej Poleev <andrejpoleev@yahoo.com>

Cc: vbarberi@pacinieditore.it

Dear Dr Andrej Poleev:

Thank you for the opportunity to review your manuscript for "Journal of Psychopathology".

I regret to inform you that I have now read your manuscript "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association." and decided that it is unsuitable for publication in IJP.

After reading the paper I decided to reject it at this point. Although the paper addresses the topic which is relevant for our journal, there are major limitations which would be hard to address in the revision process.

The editorial policy and monitoring for indexing International Journal editorial filter for an initial evaluation of manuscripts BEFORE sending to the referee, a practice increasingly difficult and costly in terms of time and attention to devote to the job evaluation.

A member of the 'Editorial Board Currency overall quality of the article and decide whether to send it to the stage of refereeing. It may happen that in this first phase also quality articles are not admitted to the second stage of evaluation. Unfortunately the high number of articles sent means that the threshold should be increased for those rejected even without an analytical assessment.

I realize that the preparation of the study and the paper included plenty of effort. The journal publishes only a small proportion of the submissions that we receive and therefore many solid papers cannot be accepted. I hope that the fact of receiving the decision soon would be of some help.

Thank you for considering IJP. I hope the outcome of this specific submission will not discourage you from the submission of future manuscripts.

With the best wishes,

Dr. Valentina Bärberi

Scientific secretariat

journal@jpsychopathol.it

Journal of Psychopathology

<http://www.jpsychopathol.net/journal>

Decision on Nature Human Behaviour submission NATHUMBEHAV-19097639
Sep 8 2019.

stavroula.kousta@nature.com <stavroula.kousta@nature.com>

To: Andrej Poleev andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr Poleev,

Thank you for submitting your Correspondence to Nature Human Behaviour. After careful consideration, I regret that we will be unable to consider it for publication.

We do not have the capacity to consider for publication more than very few Correspondence articles, so each must be of relevance to a broad cross-section of our audience. While the topic you cover is certainly of importance, we believe it would be most suitable for a journal dedicated to the publication of psychoanalytic work.

We are quite pressed for space and must therefore make very difficult decisions. Although we can't be more positive on this occasion, we thank you for your interest in the journal.

With kind regards,

Stavroula Kousta

Stavroula Kousta, PhD
Chief Editor
Nature Human Behaviour

This email has been sent through the Springer Nature Tracking System NY-610A-NPG&MTS

Decision on Manuscript ID IJP-19-215 - The International Journal of Psychoanalysis
Sep 6 2019.

The International Journal of Psychoanalysis <onbehalf@manuscriptcentral.com>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev,

I write you in regards to manuscript IJP-19-215 entitled "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association" which you submitted to The International Journal of Psychoanalysis.

After discussion, the Editors have decided not to proceed with the letter to publication as The International Journal is not the right venue. We wish you the best in placing the letter with another venue, such as perhaps, psychoanalytic society bulletins. We thank you for considering The International Journal.

Sincerely

Chris Lawrence

Journal Assistant

The International Journal of Psychoanalysis

Your Presubmission Inquiry to PLOS Medicine PMEDICINE-D-19-03213 - [EMID:b1aebf7a7ec2204d]

Sep 5 2019

PLOS Medicine <em@editorialmanager.com>

To: Andrej Poleev <andrejpoleev@yahoo.com>

Dear Dr. Poleev,

Thank you very much for your Presubmission Inquiry regarding the manuscript entitled "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association." (PMEDICINE-D-19-03213). We are grateful that you have considered PLOS Medicine for publication of your work.

As with all inquiries submitted to the journal, yours was considered in light of other papers that we receive, and our aims for the journal's magazine section. We are looking for articles aimed at a general medical audience which provide commentary, analysis, and guidance.

Having read and considered your Presubmission Inquiry, I regret to say that we do not think your manuscript would be best suited to PLOS Medicine.

I am sorry that I cannot be more positive on this occasion and hope you will consider PLOS Medicine for other submissions in the future.

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to consider your work.

Best regards,

Adya Misra,

Senior Editor

PLOS Medicine

plosmedicine@plos.org

PNAS MS# 2019-15329 Letter to Editor Decision Notification

Sep 4 2019

journalstaff@pnascentral.org <journalstaff@pnascentral.org>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev,

Thank you for your submission to PNAS. Letters to the Editor are reserved for comments on articles published in PNAS within the past six months. Your Letter does not pertain to a PNAS article. Unfortunately, we must reject your submitted letter for this reason. We appreciate your interest in PNAS and encourage you to submit in the future. Please feel free to contact our office if you have questions.

Sincerely,

PNAS Editorial Offices

New England Journal of Medicine - 19-12005

Sep 4 2019

NEJM Letter <onbehalfof@manuscriptcentral.com>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev,

Thank you for your submission, 19-12005, "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.," to the New England Journal of Medicine.

We do not consider letters of this kind for publication.

Thank you for your interest in the New England Journal of Medicine.

Sincerely,

Jacqueline Ruzicka

Editorial Assistant

New England Journal of Medicine

10 Shattuck Street

Boston, MA 02115

(617) 734-9800

Fax: (617) 739-9864

<http://www.nejm.org>

Perspectives on Psychological Science - Decision on Manuscript ID PPS-19-278

Sep 3 2019

Perspectives on Psychological Science <onbehalf@manuscriptcentral.com>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev:

Thank you for submitting your manuscript # PPS-19-278 entitled "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association." to Perspectives on Psychological Science. I am declining this manuscript without review. I do not think that this message would reach the appropriate readership through publication in Perspectives. Please keep in mind that our rejection rate is high and that, moreover, most of our rejections are based, at least in part, on our perception of a lack of fit to our particular journal. You might submit this letter to a psycho-analytically oriented journal.

Thank you for considering Perspectives on Psychological Science for the publication of your research.

Sincerely,

Laura King

Editor, Perspectives on Psychological Science

Decision on your Science Manuscript aaz3524

Sep 3 2019

Jennifer Sills <science_editors@aaas.org>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev:

Thank you for submitting your manuscript "Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association" to Science. Unfortunately, this is not the sort of work that we publish and we are thus not considering it for publication. We appreciate your interest in Science.

Sincerely,

Jennifer Sills

Science

Your Submission to The Lancet Manuscript number: THELANCET-D-19-05664
Sep 3 2019.

The Lancet Peer Review Team <eesserver@eesmail.elsevier.com>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Poleev,

Many thanks for submitting your manuscript to The Lancet. We have considered your manuscript, but our decision is that it would be better placed elsewhere.

Unfortunately, we can accept only a very small proportion of the many papers we receive each week. We are sorry to be unhelpful on this occasion, though we would like you to think of us again in the future.

Yours sincerely,

Astrid James
Deputy Editor
The Lancet

Re: The accusation of Springer. - Ticket ID [#107168]

Aug 2 2019

Springer Nature Online Service <onlineservice@springernature.com>

To: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

Dear Dr. Andrej Poleev,

Thank you for your e-mail.

Please be advised that we have contacted a colleague in the relevant team to assist with your query and will update you as soon as possible.

Please do not hesitate to contact us if we can be of any further assistance in the meantime.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us quoting your Ticket ID [#107168].

With kind regards

Jennifer Baro (Ms.)

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Managing Directors: Martin Mos, Dr. Ulrich Vest, Franciscus Vrancken Peeters

On Fri, 2 Aug at 1:25 PM , Dr. Andrej Poleev <andrejpoleev@yahoo.com> wrote:

The accusation of Springer.

<http://enzymes.at/letters/accusation.pdf>

Reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.

Referring to my letters of 26.04.2019 and 30.04.2019 addressed to the officers and members of the company and charity IPA LBG registered in England and Wales under registered numbers 3496765 and 1071752 respectively, and in consequence of disregard of my requests expressed in these letters, I announce the liquidation and the termination of the activity of the IPA LBG and its constituent organisations, and the reestablishment of the International Psychoanalytical Association.

Secondly, I confiscate all assets and property owned by IPA LBG and its constituent organisations for the purpose of said reestablishment.

Thirdly, I prohibit the usage of terms „psychoanalysis“, „psychoanalyst“ and „psychoanalytic“ and their equivalents in other languages by members of the IPA LBG, its constituent organisations, other companies, organizations and associations or by any person in relation to the professional designation.

Fourthly, to be qualified to perform psychoanalysis and to be designated as psychoanalyst, candidates should be examined by at least one supervisor and member of the reestablished International Psychoanalytical Association, and should demonstrate proficient knowledge of psychoanalysis and ability to perform it without any guidance. Every successful proof of ability will be registered, published and legally attested in order to guarantee the quality standard and individual accountability.

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Andrej Poleev". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large, prominent 'A' and 'P'.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 25.05.2019.

Andrej Poleev • Postfach 301812 • 10746 Berlin

Rhoda Bawdekar
IPA Publications Manager
Lexicon, Unit B, Book House
261a, City Road,
London EC1V 1AH
England

30.04.2019

Dear Ms Bawdekar,

I have no intent to translate my book that should include two supplementary essays, as mentioned in my book proposal, into English language, because they are intentionally written in the language of the author of The Interpretation of Dreams. Psychoanalysis is a therapeutic method that enable to identify the cause of mental disturbance by converting unconscious contents (absent, suppressed or forgotten) into conscious in the course of conversation between a patient and a psychoanalyst (Übertragung), and in this way to solve intrapsychic conflicts and amnesia, to compensate the lack of knowledge, to restore self-sufficiency and the ability for learning, thinking, retrospection, and self-healing.

Please consider the role I have to play in the course of our conversation. Your reply provides a reasonable ground to believe that you are heavily affected by repression, and therefore I remind that the International Psychoanalytical Association was founded by Sigmund Freud 1910 in order to promote his method {1–2}, and therefore it is the duty of the International Psychoanalytical Association to act in compliance with his intent. Due to extraordinary importance of my book, I expect from the International Psychoanalytical Association the publication of a print edition of my book including prior giving me all possible assistance in preparing of my book for printing.

Dr. Andrej Poleev

References.

1. Sigmund Freud. Erinnern, Wiederholen und Durcharbeiten. Internationale Zeitschrift für Ärztliche Psychoanalyse, Bd. 2 (6), 1914, S. 485-91.

„Endlich hat sich die konsequente heutige Technik herausgebildet, bei welcher der Arzt auf die Einstellung eines bestimmten Moments oder Problems verzichtet, sich damit begnügt, die jeweilige psychische Oberfläche des Analysierten zu studieren, und die Deutungskunst wesentlich dazu benützt, um die an dieser hervortretenden Widerstände zu erkennen und dem Kranken bewußtzumachen. Es stellt sich dann eine neue Art von Arbeitsteilung her: Der Arzt deckt die dem Kranken unbekanntem Widerstände auf; sind diese erst bewältigt, so erzählt der Kranke oft ohne alle Mühe die vergessenen Situationen und Zusammenhänge. Das Ziel dieser Techniken ist natürlich unverändert geblieben. Deskriptiv: die Ausfüllung der Lücken der Erinnerung, dynamisch: die Überwindung der Verdrängungswiderstände.“

2. Sigmund Freud. Zur Geschichte der psychoanalytischen Bewegung, 1914.

Die Form einer offiziellen Vereinigung hielt ich für notwendig, weil ich den Mißbrauch fürchtete, welcher sich der Psychoanalyse bemächtigen würde, sobald sie einmal in die Popularität geriete. Es sollte dann eine Stelle geben, welcher die Erklärung zustände: Mit all dem Unsinn hat die Analyse nichts zu tun, das ist nicht die Psychoanalyse. In den Sitzungen der Ortsgruppen, aus denen sich die internationale Vereinigung zusammensetzte, sollte gelehrt werden, wie die Psychoanalyse zu betreiben sei, und sollten Ärzte ihre Ausbildung finden, für deren Tätigkeit eine Art von Garantie geleistet werden konnte. Auch schien es mir wünschenswert, daß sich die Anhänger der Psychoanalyse zum freundschaftlichen Verkehr und zur gegenseitigen Unterstützung zusammenfänden, nachdem die offizielle Wissenschaft den großen Bann über sie ausgesprochen und den Boykott über die Ärzte und Anstalten verhängt hatte, die sie übten. Dies alles und nichts anderes wollte ich durch die Gründung der »Internationalen Psychoanalytischen Vereinigung« erreichen.

Rhoda Bawdekar <Rhoda@ipa.world> Apr 29 at 5:25 PM

To Journal Enzymes ISSN 1867-3317

CC Gabriela Legorreta

Dear Andrej Poleev,

Many thanks for your interest in submitting a book proposal. At this stage we receive applications in English only. Are you able to translate the two essays that you have sent through?

Many thanks in advance,

Rhoda

Rhoda Bawdekar

Web and Publications Manager

+44 20 8446 8324

<https://www.ipa.world>

Unit B, Book House, 261a City Road, London, EC1V 1AH

The International Psychoanalytical Association ("IPA") is registered in England as a company limited by guarantee (no. 3496765), and as a charity (no.1071752); whose registered address is IPA, Lexicon, Unit B Book House, 261a City Road, London EC1V 1AH, United Kingdom.

Andrej Poleev • Postfach 301812 • 10746 Berlin

Rhoda Bawdekar
IPA Publications Manager
Lexicon, Unit B, Book House
261a, City Road,
London EC1V 1AH
England

26.04.2019

Please find enclosed the completed publication proposal form for following title:

Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis.

The Author.

IPA CALL FOR PUBLICATIONS PROPOSALS FORM

TYPE OF PROPOSAL (tick appropriate)

Individual work

Themed Collection (specify theme and potential contributors)

Topical Paper

Other (Please specify)

This individual work shall be published as a print book.

TITLE: Metaanalysis of psychoanalysis (2016)

Full names of all authors / contributors

Dr. Andrej Poleev

Email: andrejpoleev@yahoo.com

(tick and enclose) Introduction: proposal description, outlining aims and scope of book

The perspective revolution of Sigmund Freud: An update.

The manuscript consists of 4 parts: The Dream; From Oedipus to Narciss; The interim summary of the endless analysis; Structures of delusion. In introductory part, I look back on the history of psychoanalysis from the beginning and until death of its founder. This reminiscence is continued in the 2nd part with the intent to examine the evolution of psychoanalytic views afterward and to overlook a conceptual whole of the psychoanalysis up to date. The next part is an attempt to merge the psychoanalytic heritage and all other fields of science. The process of mergence is inevitable in the light of recent achievements that have lead to substantial progress in our understanding of causality underlying behavior and biogenic evolution, accompanied by paradigmatic shifts and synthesis of previously dissociated scientific disciplines or fields of knowlege. The last part is focused on the questions of psychopathology and completing the line of reasoning.

Two others thematically relevant essays may compliment and supplement the main manuscript:

1. Review of the „Handbook of Antisocial personality disorder“, Schattauer, 2017. (2018)

English Abstract: The Antisocial personality disorder and several other psychiatric constructs are questioned and deconstructed in this review, that uses psychoanalytic approach to explain the nature of psychopathy and to give recommendations in this respect.

<http://enzymes.at/download/Rezension.pdf>

2. Infernal state: An essay on regression. (2019)

English Abstract: Continuing the reexamination of prevailing views, conceptions and paradigms carried out on the basis of the psychoanalytic theory, as it already has been done in previous publications, and considering great significance of the topic, I open the year 2019 with my essay on the state of psychic regression, which in my opinion is the most obvious and earnest problem of our time, and invite all scholars and qualified individuals to participate in a discussion.

<http://enzymes.at/download/regression.pdf>

x (tick and enclose) CV of all contributors (Brief: 5-6 lines)

Dr. Andrej Poleev is a russian scientist-polymath and the author of several books written in Russian and German.

CV: <http://enzymes.at/download/cv.pdf>

x (tick and enclose) Table of Contents: As indicated above.

x (tick and enclose) 1-2 chapters: As indicated above.

x (tick and enclose) Bibliography for author/editors/contributors

IMPORTANT: Proposals sent to the IPA will not be accepted if they are also under consideration by other publishing houses. Proposals are only accepted in English.

Andrej Poleev • Postfach 301812 • 10746 Berlin

IPA Accounts Department
Lexicon, Unit B, Bookhouse
261a City Road
London EC1V 1AH
England

26.04.2019

Application for defrayal.

Herewith I ask the IPA to defray the cost of a personal computer that I need for psychoanalytic work, and apply for an equipment allowance. To enable purchasing, please transfer EUR 1.500 to the account number IBAN DE24700905000001906534 BIC GENODEF1S04 (Sparda-Bank Munich).

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Andrej Poleev". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Dr. Andrej Poleev